

THE STRESS-STRAIN CURVE OF CHARACTERISTICS FOR DIFFERENT MATERIAL TYPES AND THEIR APPLICATION IN THE ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF STRUCTURES

Dr. Riya Dey¹, Sovan Patra², Rajarshi Basu³,

Associate Professor¹, Assistant Professor², Assistant Professor³

Civil engineering Department¹, Mechanical Engineering Department^{2&3}.

Global Institute of Management & Technology, Krishnanagar^{1,2&3}, West Bengal, India.

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ABSTRACT

Super elasticity was clearly evident under tensile strain of up to around 5%, but not under compressive strain, due to the presence of residual strain. The yield strength in compression is almost two times of tension yielding under the strain rate tested. SMA was applied to two structural elements in order to give a self-restoration and large deformability to building structures: SMA device for residential houses and concrete beam with SMA R-bars. Both applications were verified by seismic response analysis and model experiments to have a sufficient restoration capacity and large plastic deformability. Mechanical properties of shape memory alloy (hereinafter referred to as SMA) bars were investigated for their structural use of buildings and two examples of SMA in super elasticity phase applied to structural elements are proposed. The static and dynamic loading tests on SMA bars demonstrated that the stress-strain curve for tensile stress is completely different from that for compressive stress, irrespective of whether the load is static or dynamic in nature.

Keywords - Residual strain , SMA ,tensile stress ,compressive stress, yield strength.

INTRODUCTION

SMA exhibits differing properties including a shape memory effect, super elasticity, and a behavior between the two according to the temperature of the material, as shown in Figure 1. Since SMA is known to have stable super elasticity within a temperature range of approximately 30 degrees centigrade above the reversible transformation temperature, this material has sufficient potential as a super elastic material for use in construction under the temperature of a construction environment, provided the transformation temperature is suitably controlled. It is already known that SMA wires exhibit super elasticity under tensile stress having a stress-strain curve shaped like a flag (Figure 2)[1-9]. Since SMA shows super elastic behavior over large strain ranges of up to about 5 %, a significant amount of deformation recovery is possible. This makes SMA a candidate material as a self-restoration member in structure if the transformation temperature can be suitably controlled. In consideration of the building structural use, the larger capacity of SMA will be needed than thin wires. Therefore, the mechanical properties of SMA bars are investigated in this study. Based on these results, two examples of SMA material in super elasticity phase applied to structural elements are proposed and its self-restoration capacity is verified by analysis and experiments.

Figure 1 : Stress-strain relation of SMA wire under room temperature 16 degree centigradestress strain property of SMA bars

LOADING TEST

Little is known about how SMA behaves when subjected to compression. This experiment was designed to determine the stress-strain relationship in SMA bars in super elastic alloy phase when subjected to compressive and tensile forces. The alloy composition and manufacturing conditions were carefully selected so that the experimental specimen would exhibit super elastic properties at room temperature. The exact composition was Ni 54.51%, Co 1.48%, and the remainder Ti. Table 1 shows transformation temperatures as measured using a differential scanning calorimeter.

The specimen was a 16 mm length of bar of diameter 7 mm, which was fabricated from a parallel section of a longer length of bar of diameter 17 mm. The top and bottom ends were clamped in hydraulic chucks with the centers perfectly aligned. Axial forces were then applied. (Hereunder, “specimen” refers to the parallel piece of 7-mm diameter bar.) To measure the strain on and temperature of the specimen, two strain gauges, one of which also doubled as a thermocouple, were affixed on either side of the center of the parallel section, and an 8 mm extensometer was attached across the gauges.

The ambient temperature was around 26 degree centigrade during the experiment. The readings from the two facing strain gauges were monitored to see whether the test piece was centrally loaded. The readings deviated from one another only very slightly during the experiment. Similarly, eccentricity under the compression load did not reach significant levels. Both static and dynamic loads were applied to the specimen by controlling the distance between the chucks with respect to displacement and velocity. The load waveform used a triangular displacement-time relationship for both static and dynamic loads.

TABLE 1 TRANSFORMATION TEMPERATURE OF SMA BAR TESTED

transformation temperature	Martensitic transformation start temperature	Martensitic transformation end temperature	Reversible transformation start temperature	Reversible transformation end temperature
centigrade	Ms=51	Mf=-38.0	As=17.8	Af=43.2

Static tensile property

Figure 3 shows the stress-strain relationship for the static tensile test. The experiment began with three repetitions at each level (0%–1%, 0%–2%, etc.), as shown by the solid line. The specimen was then placed in a hot water bath at 50 degree centigrade (hotter than the temperature at the end of the reverse transformation) for ten minutes, and repetitions were performed during unloading (at 0%–2%, 2%–4%, etc.). The strain generally returned to zero after each loading, clearly indicating super elastic properties. Strain hardening can be observed from around 4% strain, where the curve gradient starts increasing. A very small amount of residual strain was observed after removal of the strain (approximately 4.5%).

Figure 2 : Stress-strain relations for static tension test.

Static compressive property

As Figure 4 shows, the experiment was conducted in two stages. The first stage consisted of three repetitions at each of the target strain values: 0% – 1%, 0% – 2%, 0% – 3%, 0% – 4%, and 0% – 5% (actually closer to 6%). The specimen was then placed in hot water (50 degree centigrade) for ten minutes, and three repetitions were performed at each of the following target strain values: 0% – 2%, 2% – 4%, and 4% – 6%. Since the load was controlled by the distance between the two chucks, the paths or trajectories the stress-strain curve took were not exactly the same for all the sets of tests, because of the residual strain that remained in the test piece after removal of the load.

Figure 4 shows the results of both the first half of the experiment (solid line) and the second half (broken line), with the second half results shifted in parallel with the strain axis at the conclusion of the first half. The stress-strain curve for compression forces differs in shape from the tension curve in Figure 3. The strain value shows no sign of the super elasticity which would cause it to revert to zero upon removal of the load. The residual strain in fact resembles the stress-strain relationship for cold-formed carbon steel.

FIGURE 3 : STRESS-STRAIN RELATION FOR STATIC COMPRESSION TEST

Static tensile-compressive property

Figure 5 shows the results of the tensile-compressive tests. The stress-strain relationship differs in many respects (yield strength, rigidity of plateau area after yielding, final strain value after removal of load) between the tension and the compression tests. Residual strain was observed after compression, but this could be negated almost completely by then applying a tensile strain that was greater (in absolute terms) than the compression strain that caused the residue.

a) FOR STATIC COMPRESSION-TENSION B) FOR STATIC TENSION-COMPRESSION

FIGURE 4 : STRESS-STRAIN RELATION FOR STATIC COMPRESSION-TENSION

Dynamic tensile-compressive property

Energy absorption under cyclic loading

The load waveform was triangular. The amplitude was varied at $\pm 1\%$, $\pm 2\%$, and $\pm 4\%$, in that order. Four different loading frequencies (0.066 Hz, 0.33 Hz, 1.64 Hz, and 3.3 Hz) were used at each amplitude. Ten repetitions were performed for each set of conditions. Figures 7-a and 7-b represent the repetition loop area E shown in Figure 6 divided by the area E_o of the rectangle inscribed by the loop, for 2% and 4% amplitude, respectively. Energy absorption per cycle was determined by comparing the loop area for a single cycle with the area of the rectangle that circumscribes the loop, as described above. (The equivalentattenuation method cannot be applied directly in this situation due to differences in the load-carrying capacity at peak times between the tension and compression sides in the stress-strain curve for SMA.)

Energy absorption rate per cycle differs according to the strain amplitude: at 2% strain amplitude, the higher strain velocity causes the energy absorption rate to decrease, while at 4% strain amplitude, there was no simple correlation between the strain velocity and the rate of energy absorption.

Figure 5 : Definitions for E/Eo

a) for 2% amplitude of strain b) for 4% amplitude of strain

Figure 6 :E/Eo vs. loading cycle

Strain rate effects on Young's modulus & yield strength

Figure 7 presents effects of strain rate on Young's modulus and yield strength defined as 0.2 % offset value. The obvious relation cannot be notified between strain rate and these values. Yield strength in compression is almost two times of tension yielding under the strain rate tested.

A) YOUNG'S MODULUS VS. STRAIN RATE B) YIELD STRENGTH VS. STRAIN RATE

FIGURE 7 :EFFECT OF STRAIN RATE ON YOUNG'S MODULUS & YIELD STRENGTH

SMA DEVICE FOR RESIDENTIAL HOUSES

BRACE TYPE SMA DEVICE

SMA bars clearly show super elasticity in tension and not in compression. If SMA bars are used as a tension member, it would effectively control a displacement response of structures and return their lateral drift to zero after earthquakes. Then, a response control device with SMA bars is designed for low-storied houses as the followings: 1) SMA devices carry lateral forces, and beam-to-column frame supports vertical loads, 2) the size of SMA bars is designed so that the device has its required lateral stiffness and strength, 3) SMA bars are effective only in tension, 4) elastic design is applied to the other part (i.e. steel frame and joints) of the device under the yield strength of SMA bars (see Figure 8).

beam-to-column frame

set up into frame

SMA-device with steel frame

FIGURE 8: SMA DEVICE AND ITS SET UP INTO A BEAM-TO-COLUMN FRAME

Seismic response of structure with SMA device

In order to conform the performance of SMA devices under severe earthquakes, the response of a structure with SMA devices was analyzed to El Centro NS wave of 340 gals' maximum input. It is assumed that beam-to-column joints of the frame are pin-joint, the frame of the device behaves in elastic and the braceswork only in tension. Therefore, the restoring force characteristic of the structure can be assumed to be similar to stress-strain curve of SMA, as shown in Figure 10-b. This multi-linear model is based on the material test result of SMA bar introduced in the former chapter (see Figure 10-a). A single degree of freedom model with 0.5 second natural period, 5% viscous damping and lateral yield shear Q_y of 40% of total structure weight was selected as an analytical model, which represents low-storied houses. The response is drawn in Figure 11 in comparison with the system of bi-linear restoring force characteristics. The analysis demonstrates that SMA devices return lateral drift of the structure to zero, on the contrary bi-linear system has some amount of story drift after the quake. But the maximum lateral displacement of the structure with SMA devices is about 1.5 times of the bi-linear model, because of lack of energy dissipation.

Figure 9: Restoring characteristic model of a structure with SMA devices (Stress-strain curve of SMA bar)

Figure 10 : Time history of Response of SMA-model & bi-linear model

Loading test of mortar-beam with SMA R-bars

SMA wires having a length of 500 mm and a diameter of 2.0 mm were selected as the materials with the maximum diameter obtainable. The transformation temperature was set to exhibit super elasticity at room temperature. Since SMA wires having a diameter of 2.0 mm were used as the main bars, mortar was used instead of concrete. The test specimens were formed to have a square cross-section with 100-mm sides. For comparison purposes, a test specimen was prepared using steel wire (cold-formed) with a diameter of

1.9 mm as the main bars. Figure 13 shows the details and dimensions of the specimens. Since the super elasticity of the SMA makes the bending process difficult, steel blocks were provided on the ends of the beam and the main bars were fixed in holes in the steel blocks through the frictional forces generated among screws, the steel blocks, and the wires. The tests confirmed that the SMA wires did not come out of the steel blocks prior to tensile fracture of the wires. Figures 2 and 14 show the stress-strain relationship of the SMA wires and steel wires, while Table 2 lists the mechanical properties of the material. Here, Young's modulus of the SMA wires is about 1/4 that of the steel wires and the yield strength is about 17% less. A simple bending test was conducted in which a concentrated load is applied to the mid span of the beam orthogonal to the material's axis, while both ends of the specimen are supported by pins.

Table 2 Mechanical properties of material (unit : N/mm²)

Material	Young's modulus	Yield strength	Maximum strength
SMA wire	49,000	580	1,220
Steel wire	167,000	676	576
Mortar	20,000	-	26.5

Figure 11: Stress-strain relation of steel wires in comparison with a part of SMA wire's curveLoad carrying.

PROPERTY OF MORTAR-BEAM WITH SMA R-BARS

Figure 11 shows the load-deflection (rotation angle of the material ends) relationship for each test specimen. In the test specimen using SMA bars (SMA5), an abrupt load loss occurred directly after a crack was generated, since the mortar had no more resistance to tensile stress. As deflection increased after this point, the SMA bars began to take on the burden of the tensile stress and gradually increased in resisting force. Residual deflection after unloading was small, even when the deflection was large at the loading peak. The specimen reached a maximum strength when the rotation angle of its ends was 0.13 radians. At the maximum strength, compressive failure occurred in the mortar around the loading point in the center of the beam. However, the SMA bars did not rupture. The deforming capacity of the SMA wires at their maximum strength exceeded ten times that of the beam using steel wires (STE).

The test specimen with steel wires as main bars had rigidity during unloading approximately equivalent to elastic stiffness, while showing a tendency to increase in deflection during hysteresis peaks and to increase in residual deflection after unloading. The test specimen reached its ultimate strength at a rotation angle of 0.008 radians. Subsequently, the resisting force began to degrade and, at a rotation angle of 0.016 radians, main bars in the center of the beam ruptured in the tension side.

Since an external transverse force was applied to the center of the simply supported beam, a single crack was generated on the tension side around the critical section of the beam for two specimens. The crack width increased along with an increase in deflection caused by the applied force.

Fig -12 shows the variations in crack widths for each test specimen. The residual crack widths after unloading were roughly uniform in SMA5, with no relation to the crack widths during hysteresis peaks. On the other hand, residual crack widths tended to increase in the specimen using steel wires as main bars along with an increase in the generated crack widths.

Figure 12 : Load vs. rotation angle of the beams.

CONCLUSION

This study first looked at the stress-strain relationship of Ti-Ni shape memory alloy for a columned specimen. The experiment was conducted with the specimen at the super-elastic-alloy-phase temperature. The specimen was subjected to static and dynamic compressive and tensile stress. The test results demonstrated that the stress-strain curve for tensile stress is completely different from that for compressive stress, irrespective of whether the load is static or dynamic in nature. Super elasticity was clearly evident under tensile strain of up to around 5%, but not under compressive strain, due to the presence of residual strain. The yield strength in compression is almost two times of tension yielding under the strain rate tested.

Second, SMA was applied to two structural elements in order to give a self-restoration and large deformability to building structures. The braced frame type devices with SMA were designed to control seismic response of residential houses. Their performance was verified by seismic response analysis to return story drift of structures to zero after earthquakes, effectively.

The mortar beam with SMA wires was examined to verify the potential self-restoration capacity. The test results revealed that the beam with SMA wires almost recovered after incurring an extremely large deformation, in comparison with that of the beam with steel wires. This result suggests that the SMA R-bars is added self-restoration capacity to concrete beams.

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